

N- α -Pyridyl-N'-Benzoyl Thiourea as a Chelating Agent for the Determination of Iridium

S. C. SHOME, M. MAZUMDAR and P. K. HALDAR

Presidency College, Calcutta-700 073, India

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N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea (PBT) is recommended as the most suitable reagent for either gravimetric or spectrophotometric determination of iridium. The precipitate formed by the reagent with iridium(III) at pH 4.2-5.86 can be weighed as Ir (C₁₃H₁₀N₃OS)₃. The base metals do not interfere with the gravimetric determination of iridium in presence of masking agents. Interferences of platinum(IV) and palladium(III) are avoided by prior precipitation of the metal ions with PBT in 1.5(N) hydrochloric acid medium. Ruthenium(III) and osmium(VI) when reduced with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sulphur dioxide respectively, produce no interference in the gravimetric determination of iridium. The iridium-PBT complex can be extracted with chloroform at pH 5.2-6.4 for the spectrophotometric determination of iridium. The extract shows maximum absorbance at 350 nm, obeys Beer's law at the same wavelength over the concentration range of the metal from 0.816 μ g/ml to 8.16 μ g/ml. By the use of PBT, iridium can be spectrophotometrically determined in the presence of large amounts of all the base metals and noble metals except rhodium.

FEW organic reagents have been used for either gravimetry or spectrophotometry of iridium.

Benzyltriphenyl phosphonium chloride¹, tetraphenyl arsonium chloride¹, 2-mercaptobenzothiazole², 2-mercaptobenzimidazole³ were employed for the precipitation of iridium, but none of the reagents is suitable for direct gravimetry of the metal. Although *p*-nitro dimethyl aniline⁴, dianisidine⁵, tetraphenyl phosphonium bromide⁶ and oximidobenzotetronic acid⁷ were recommended for the spectrophotometry of the metal, their colour reactions are, however, easily affected by slight change in experimental conditions and the methods suffer from serious interferences caused by the presence of common acid radicals and other platinum metals. Iridium was determined by both gravimetry and spectrophotometry using thiosalicylamide⁸ as the chelating agent. Some other platinum metals, however interfere.

In the present investigation N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea⁹⁻¹² (PBT) has been found effective for the gravimetric as well as spectrophotometric determination of iridium. Iridium(III) is quantitatively precipitated with the reagent in the pH range 4.2-5.86 as an orange yellow complex which is stable towards heat, light, air and can be weighed directly as Ir (C₁₃H₁₀N₃OS)₃ for gravimetric determination of the metal. For the spectrophotometric determination of iridium the metal complex is extracted with chloroform at pH 5.2-6.4. Iridium can be determined with the reagent by both gravimetry and spectrophotometry in the presence of a large excess of base metals and noble metals except rhodium.

Experimental

Apparatus, Reagents and Chemicals :

A Carl Zeiss spectrophotometer, Model PMQ II, with 1-cm quartz cells, was used for transmittance measurements. A Cambridge Bench Model pH meter equipped with glass and calomel electrodes was used for pH measurements.

A standard iridium(III) solution was prepared by dissolving iridium trichloride, monohydrate (E. Merck) in dilute hydrochloric acid and standardizing the solution by hydrolytic precipitation method. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared by dissolving known amounts of the corresponding pure salts in distilled water or dilute hydrochloric acid.

All the reagents and chemicals used were of A. R. grade.

Properties and composition of the complex :

The iridium-PBT complex is stable towards heat, light, air and slowly decomposes at 172°. The complex was analysed for iridium, nitrogen and sulphur, and the analytical results were as follows :

Percentage found : Ir = 20.09, N = 13.19, S = 9.96.

Percentage required for Ir(C₁₃H₁₀N₃OS)₃ :

Ir = 20.0, N = 13.12, S = 10.0

Gravimetric Determination of Iridium :

Iridium was quantitatively precipitated with PBT from solutions adjusted to pH ranging from 4.2 to 5.86, and the required reagent concentration in the supernatant liquid for complete precipitation of the metal was 0.01% (W/V).

Procedure : A known amount of solution containing 4.00-12.00 mg of iridium(III) was diluted to 150 ml in a beaker, heated to boiling and 8-10 ml of 1% solution of PBT in 30% acetic acid solution were added per 10 mg of the metal. The mixture was stirred for 10 minutes and the pH was slowly adjusted to 4.2-5.86 with 4(N) ammonia solution and dilute hydrochloric acid. The mixture was again heated and stirred for 15 minutes when the orange yellow iridium complex was precipitated. The beaker with its contents was allowed to stand for 5 hours on boiling water bath with occasional stirring. The complex was filtered through a sintered glass crucible (No. 4), washed with hot water, dried at 110°-115°, cooled in a desiccator and weighed as Ir (C₁₈H₁₀N₃OS)₃.

Effect of diverse ions :

Iridium was determined with PBT in different solutions containing a known amount of iridium(III) and the requisite amount of the base metal in presence of a suitable masking agent, by following the above procedure.

To separate iridium from palladium(II) or platinum(IV), the latter metal ions were first precipitated with PBT from 1.5(N) hydrochloric acid medium and filtered. Iridium was then determined in the filtrate with PBT. The interferences of ruthenium(III) and osmium(VI) were avoided by their prior reduction with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sulphur dioxide respectively. Rhodium(III), however interferes. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Precision and accuracy : The relative standard deviation and relative mean error for the gravimetric determination of the metal with PBT were calculated and found to be 0.30% and 0.12% respectively.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Iridium :

The extraction of the iridium-PBT complex was found to be quantitative when the pH of the aqueous layer was maintained between 5.2 and 6.4. The iridium complex was completely extracted in chloroform and in isobutyl methyl ketone in presence of a few ml of ethanol. In benzene, nitrobenzene, ether and carbon-tetrachloride the complex was, however, only partially extracted.

Absorbance curves :

Absorbance curves of the extracts of iridium (III)-PBT complex in chloroform-ethanol mixture, containing varying concentrations of the metal are shown in fig. 1. The extracts show maximum absorbance at 350 nm and obey Beer's law at the same wavelength over the concentration range of iridium from 0.816 µg/ml to 8.16 µg/ml.

TABLE I—SEPARATION OF IRIIDIUM FROM DIVERSE IONS

Iridium taken=8.1 mg			
Foreign ion added (mg)	Iridium found (mg)	Foreign ion added (mg)	Iridium found (mg)
Co ³⁺ (200) ^a	8.08	UO ₂ ²⁺ (200) ^a	8.1
Ni ²⁺ (200) ^a	8.08	Th ⁴⁺ (200) ^a	8.1
Mn ²⁺ (200) ^a	8.1	V ⁵⁺ (200) ^a	8.1
Zn ²⁺ (500) ^a	8.12	Mo ⁶⁺ (200) ^a	8.08
Cd ²⁺ (200) ^b	8.1	W ⁶⁺ (200) ^a	8.08
Hg ²⁺ (100) ^b	8.12	Au ³⁺ (50) ^b	8.1
Ga ³⁺ (200) ^a	8.12	Po ₄ ³⁻ (500)	8.08
In ³⁺ (100) ^a	8.08	F ⁻ (500)	8.08
Tl ³⁺ (200) ^a	8.1	E.D.T.A ²⁻ (1000)	8.1
Cu ²⁺ (200) ^b	8.12	Pd ²⁺ (23.6)	8.08
Fe ³⁺ (200) ^b	8.12	Pt ⁴⁺ (19.4)	8.1
Pb ²⁺ (200) ^b	8.12	Ru ³⁺ (21.8)	8.08
Ti ⁴⁺ (100) ^c	8.08	Os ⁶⁺ (29.4)	8.08

a - in presence of tartrate ions
 b - in presence of E.D.T.A.
 c - in presence of fluoride ions.

Fig. 1. Absorbance curves of Iridium (III)-N-(4-pyridyl)-N'-benzoyl thiourea complex in chloroform-ethanol mixture [Ir III]: [O] = 2.45 µg/ml. [Δ] = 4.9 µg/ml [●] = 6.53 µg/ml

Procedure : A measured amount of standard iridium(III) solution was introduced in a 100-ml separatory funnel, adjusted to pH 5.2-6.4 by adding 10% sodium acetate solution and dilute hydrochloric acid, and 0.01 (M) ethanolic solution of PBT (about 10 times

the theoretical amount) was added. The separatory funnel with its contents was placed on a boiling water bath for about 45 minutes, cooled to room temperature, 5 ml of ethanol were added and mixed thoroughly. The iridium complex was then extracted 2-3 times with 5-ml portions of chloroform. The extracts were collected in a 25-ml volumetric flask and diluted to the mark with chloroform. The absorbance of the extract was measured at 350 nm against appropriate reagent blank, prepared under similar conditions.

Effect of diverse ions :

In the presence of large amounts of base metal ions, iridium was spectrophotometrically determined with PBT using a suitable masking agent like E.D.T.A., fluoride or tartrate ions. The metal was separated from palladium by preliminary extraction of the latter with PBT at pH 2.0. The interference of platinum(IV) was avoided by its prior extraction with PBT in 1.5 (N) hydrochloric acid. To avoid the interferences of ruthenium(III) and osmium(VI), preliminary reduction of these metal ions was carried out with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sulphur dioxide respectively. The tolerance limits (i.e. the concentration of diverse ions causing an error less than $\pm 2\%$ in the transmittance value) are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS IN THE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF IRIDIUM

Iridium taken = 81.6 μg			
Foreign ion added	Amount tolerated μg	Foreign ion added	Amount tolerated μg
Co ²⁺	3000 ^a	Fe ²⁺	2000 ^b
Ni ²⁺	2000 ^b	UO ₂ ²⁺	5000 ^a
Mn ²⁺	3000 ^a	Th ⁴⁺	5000 ^a
Cd ²⁺	2000 ^b	Ti ⁴⁺	2000 ^c
Hg ²⁺	500 ^b	Pb ²⁺	2000
Ga ³⁺	1000 ^a	Cu ²⁺	3000 ^b
In ³⁺	1000 ^a	Au ³⁺	500 ^b
Tl ³⁺	1000 ^a	Pd ²⁺	300
Mo ⁶⁺	500 ^a	Pt ⁴⁺	300
W ⁶	500 ^a	Ru ³⁺	250
V ⁵⁺	500 ^a	Os ⁶⁺	250

a=In presence of tartrate ions

b=In presence of E.D.T.A. ions

c=In presence of fluoride ions

Nature of the complex in solution :

The empirical formula of the iridium(III)-PBT complex was determined by the mole-ratio method of

Meyer and Ayres¹³. The results indicate that the molar ratio of the reagent to the metal ion in the iridium complex is 3:1. The results were verified by the slope-ratio method.

Molar absorptivity, Sensitivity, Precision and Accuracy :

The molar absorptivity of the iridium-PBT complex, the sensitivity of the colour reaction, the coefficient of variation and the relative mean error for the determination of the metal with PBT were found to be $1.8 \times 10^4 \text{ l. mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $0.01 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, 0.44% and 0.21% respectively.

Discussion

In the past attempts were made by various investigators to employ organic reagents for the gravimetry and spectrophotometry of iridium. The methods were, however, time consuming, requiring close control of the conditions of the reactions and the determination of the metal was interfered by commonly associated diverse ions. Moreover, none of these reagents formed any directly weighable complex with iridium. PBT offers a simple and rapid method for the gravimetric and spectrophotometric determination of iridium(III) with high accuracy. The most advantage of the use of PBT is that it can be applied in the gravimetric and spectrophotometric determination of iridium in the presence of large amounts of base metals and noble metals except rhodium(III).

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